

Assessment of In-containment Accidental Source Term for Small Modular Reactor

Abdul Rab Asary ^{1*}, Abdul Basit ², Abdul Samad ³, Atia Perveen ⁴

¹ Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie per l'Energia e la Mobilità Sostenibili (STEMS) - Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, 80125 Napoli, Italy - University of Naples Parthenope Italy, 80133 Napoli, Italy

² Sabancı University, 34956 Tuzla, İstanbul, Turkey

³ NED university of Engineering and technology, 79270, Karachi, Pakistan.

⁴ East China Normal University, Shanghai 200062, China

Accepted October 10,2021
Published October 19,2021

*Corresponding Author:
Abdul Rab Asary
abdulrabasary@hotmail.com
[m](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5579189)

DOI :<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5579189>

Pages: 67-84

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):
A. Abdul Rab, A. Basit, A. Samad, P. Atia. (2021)
Assessment of In-containment
Accidental Source Term for
Small Modular Reactor. *North
American Academic Research*,
4(10), 67-84. doi:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5579189>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

1. Introduction

The radioactive material is released from the containment during nuclear accidents as in the case of the Three Mile Island accident. This is often known as radiological release to the environment. This radiological release to the environment can be evaluated through leakage rate from the containment and radioactive inventory within the containment. This radioactive inventory within the containment is also known as In-containment accidental source term. The word source term is used for fission products that release from the core into the

ABSTRACT

Many studies have been completed for analysis of source terms for commercial and research nuclear reactors. No studies have been done for small modular reactors (SMR). Different fission products release from the reactor core into the containment during a nuclear accident like TMI-2. Assessment of fission products in the containment is necessary for better design of future nuclear reactors. To evaluate the fission products, a MATLAB program is developed using Runge-Kutta 4th order method. This program evaluates four elements of each isotope in the containment air and on the containment surface. Results show that the activity of fission products in the containment air is high as compared to the surface. The activity in the containment air is an increase for some time then decrease gradually concerning time. The behavior of fission products on the containment surface is the same but different in activity level except for noble gases, their activity increases as time increase. Moreover, containment spray also helps to remove fission products up to 2 orders of magnitude which satisfied our results according to the NUREG-1465 report. In the end, a comparison of SMR is investigated with research reactor and commercial reactor. The model can also be used to evaluate the containment performance and other actinides fission products for SMR.

Keywords: CONTAINMENT SURFACE, CONTAINMENT VOLUME, FISSION PRODUCTS, SMR

containment (1). Analysis of source terms is very necessary for research reactors and commercial reactors in case of severe nuclear accidents (2). Three Mile Island (TMI-2) accident was unpredicted to every mind, happens due to loss of coolant process on March 28, 1979, at Harrisburg Pennsylvania. About 70% noble gases, 20% iodine, and 40% cesium release to reactor containment buildings. On April 26, 1986, a severe accident was occurred at Chernobyl nuclear power plant due to a heavy core meltdown process that occurred in the RBMK reactor. The radioactivity was detected 1000 km from the Chernobyl Nuclear Reactor at the Forsmark power plant. Recently, March 11, 2011, was the most severe nuclear accident that happened due to a natural disaster in the nuclear history at Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant. There was six-unit at Daiichi station affected due to the tsunami and earthquake. Tsunami flood first destroyed the backup diesel generator that was connected to passive safety systems. Later on, the core heated up and at the same time, the earthquake fluctuated. Then, core meltdown started, zirconium reacted with water to produce a big hydrogen explosion with shock waves that destroyed three units completely and some of them partially (3). During nuclear accidents, containment and natural process play a vital role in the reduction of fission products. The transport of fission products within the containment can be described by many processes like aerosol agglomeration, containment deposition. Shared Cost Action Reactor Safety Program (1985-1987) was conducted to analyze the fission products and aerosol behavior within the containment (4). *Brillant et al.* (5) have reported three types of fission products. They are named as highly volatile (I, Br, Sc, Rb, Te, Xe, Kr, Cu, Sb, Ag), semi-volatile (Sr, Ru, Ba, La, Eu, Ce, Mo), and low volatile FP (Nd, Pu, Np, Nb, Zr, Dy, Rh, Pd, As, U, Pm, Tc, Er, Am, Y, Ho, Tm, Sm, Zn, Tb, Gd, Ga, In, Ge, Sn). Eight groups of FP have been reported in NUREG-1465 namely as noble gases, halogens, alkali metals, tellurium, barium & strontium, noble metals, lanthanides, and cerium group (1). Many studies have been done to investigate the fission products for nuclear reactors. *Saeed* (6) have investigated the fission products under loss of coolant accident for material test reactor Known as Pakistan Atomic Research Reactor (PARR-1). Before the same type of study was examined by *Ullah et al.* (7) and *Waqar et al.* (8). *Mirza et al.* (9) have calculated radionuclide inventories in discharged fuel for HEU and LEU miniature neutron source reactor. *Anvari et al.* (10) have evaluated the total effective dose for Tehran Research Reactor (TRR). Later the same type of study was assessed by *Sadeghi et al.* (11). *Raza et al.* (12) have examined atmospheric dispersion modeling for Pakistan Atomic Research Reactor. Some studies have also made on Greek Research Reactor. *Pappas et al.* (13) have calculated source term for Greek Research Reactor and radiological consequences of eighteen scenario under severe accident condition. Source term analysis have also done for 1000 MWe pressurized water reactor under severe accident condition (14).

During the loss of coolant accident, some fission products mix up with coolant and steam. Due to gravity action, some fission products interact with containment surface and most of them go to containment air. So, containment surface and air are important for the calculation of fission products. Here, containment air activity is considered as volumetric activity. All previous studies have been performed for research reactors or 1000 MWe reactors under severe accident conditions. Loss of coolant accident is taken as reference accident for this literature. These studies concentrate only on volumetric activity within the containment. In

this research work, source term analysis is investigated for SMR. MATLAB software is used for simulation which evaluates the activity within containment air and on the surface also.

In this research work, modeling and simulation of in-containment accidental sources for SMR have been assessed. Loss of coolant accident is taken as reference for 300 MWe pressurized water reactor. Modeling and simulation of SMR are carried by a model which calculates fission products within the containment surface as well on the volume. Runge Kutta's 4th order method is used to evaluate the fission products. In the end, a comparison of 300 MWe is made with a 10 MWe research reactor (PARR-1) and a 1000 MWe pressurized water reactor.

2. Description of Pressurized Water Reactor

PWR is used for the production of electricity. Pressurized water reactor consists of three main buildings namely reactor building, auxiliary building, turbine building. Reactor building consists of mostly nuclear components and the other two types contain non-nuclear components. Reactor building composed of a reactor core, control rods, core flood tank, steam generator, pressurizer, reactor coolant pump, sump pump, rupture disk. Turbine building composed of a turbine, generator, condensate pump, demineralized, emergency feedwater pump. Auxiliary building composed of radiation waste storage tank, makeup water tank, waste gas decay tank (15). The reference plant has a 300 MWe capacity that uses UO₂ fuel and zircaloy as cladding material. There are 194 fuel assemblies and 264 rods per assembly. The core height is 4.17m and the diameter is 3.33m. The power plant has a 1000 MW_{th} capacity. Table 1 shows the design parameters of SMR.

Table 1. SMR Design Parameters [17]

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Value</i>
Thermal Capacity	1000
Electric Capacity	300
Specific power (MWth/kg U)	33
Power density (MWth/m ³)	102
Core height (m)	4.17
Core diameter (m)	3.33
Number of fuel assemblies	194
Rods per assembly	264
Fuel type	UO ₂
Clad type	Zircaloy
Lattice pitch (mm)	12.6
Fuel rod outer diameter (mm)	9.5
Average enrichment (w/o)	3
Flow rate (mg/s)	18.3
Linear heat rate (kW/m ²)	17.5
Coolant pressure (MPa)	18.5
Inlet coolant temperature (°C)	293
Outlet coolant temperature (°C)	329

3. Severe Accident

Nine types of an accident have been defined by U.S Nuclear Regularity Commission (USNRC). Loss of Coolant Accident is the 8th category accident which is considered a severe type of accident. This type of accident happens due to a rupture in the primary coolant pipe. Just 2 s after the break, a huge mass of steam and water expelled out from the ruptured pipe which makes pressure difference within the reactor core. It takes only 30 s that core inventory ejected from reactor core into containment. Temperature and pressure reach the highest point in the containment. This situation is called blowdown of accident and after 100 s water comes out of very quickly from core including melted fuel and molten core material. This type of situation happened at unit 2 of the Three Mile Island power plant. The peak design pressure was 50 to 65 psi which means that containment could operate for a very long period at this pressure. If pressure increased just 3 factors above the design pressure, then as a result containment would break. Although the Three Mile Island accident was threatened to whole containment building its pressure reaches only 29 psi which was very low according to design pressure This type is called severe loss of coolant accident (16).

4. Analytical Approach

An analytical approach has been taken for the analysis of fission products in the containment 1000 MWe PWR. *Mehboob* (14) has presented the following mathematical models for the analysis of source terms.

4.1 In-containment Air

Let $q_v(t)$ is the activity in the containment air and $q_s(t)$ is the activity on the containment surface therefore the total rate of change in activity in the air is

$$\frac{dq_v(t)}{dt} = -\lambda q_v(t) - u_t \frac{S}{V} q_v(t) - \alpha \frac{F}{V} q_v(t) - R_{air} \frac{\eta_{rc}}{V} q_v(t) - \frac{L_r}{V} q_v(t) + r \frac{S}{V} q_v(t) + Q(t) \quad (1)$$

$$\alpha = \left\{ HE_i \text{ for iodine, } \frac{3hE_a}{2d} \text{ for solid fission products} \right\}$$

First-term on right side of Eq. (1) represents the decay of isotopes, 2nd term is the removal of iodine by a deposition process, 3rd term is removal through containment spray process, 4th term is removal through recirculation process, 5th term is leakage rate through exhaust building, 6th term is resuspension of iodine on the surface and 7th term is a quantity that releases from damage core along with water, fuel, and zirconium. Where S is containment surface, V is containment volume, λ is decay constant, u_t is deposition velocity, R_{air} is recirculation flow rate, η_{rc} is recirculation filtrate efficiency, L_r is leakage rate from the exhaust, and r is resuspension.

4.2 On-Containment Surface

The rate of change in concentration of activity on containment surface

$$\frac{dq_s(t)}{dt} = u_t q_v(t) - r q_s(t) \quad (2)$$

The first term on the right side of Eq. (2) is the deposition process of iodine on containment volume and the second term is resuspension of iodine on the containment surface.

4.3 Leakage from Reactor Core

The $Q(t)$ [Bq/s.m³] is the amount of molten corium that comes out from the damaged core. This amount has also been suggested *Mehboob* (14) is given as follows

$$Q(t) = (1 - f_x)A_c \times f_f \times f_p \times f_c \frac{K}{V} e^{(-w_x t)} \quad (3)$$

The $f_p = (1 - CRF)$ is release fraction from the coolant into containment volume, CRF is coolant retention factor, f_f is fuel release fraction, f_c is core damage fraction, f_x is an airborne fraction, $(1 - f_x)A_c \times f_f \times f_p \times f_c \times e^{(-w_x t)}$ is an activity that releases from damage core into the containment environment, w_x is mixing rate and A_c is total activity before the accident. The exponential factor in Eq. (3) describes quantity that decreases with time with the mixing rate. Where K is the normalization constant which is equal to w_x the time-dependent source balance equation is given by

$$A_c = f_x A_c + (1 - f_x) A_c K \int_0^T e^{w_x t} dt \quad (4)$$

$$K = \frac{w_x \times (w_x / T)}{w_x - w_x / T} \quad (5)$$

In Eq. (4) & Eq. (5), the f_x is an activity that becomes available just after the accident, and $(1 - f_x)$ is that activity that is transmitted from coolant to containment air. The integration over large time is $T \approx w_x$, then normalization constant becomes equal to w_x as time-dependent function. Table 2 shows the important parameters used for isotopes and containment (14). Table 3 shows the initial core inventory calculated by Iqbal (17) and decay constant values.

TABLE 2. Released percentage forms for the containment (14)

Parameters	Symbols	Values
Containment volume	V (m ³)	57600
Containment surface	S (m ²)	34374
Leakage rate from exhaust	L_r (m ³ /s)	1.0-14.15
Recirculation rate	R_{air} (m ³ /s)	1-4.179
Recirculation filtration efficiency	η_{rc} (%)	10-90%
Spray flow rate	F (m ³ /s)	0.1-1.0
Deposition velocity	μ_i (m/s)	0.00055
Resuspension rate	r (s ⁻¹)	0.1
Core damage percentage	f_c (%)	50
Fuel release percentage	f_f (%)	90
Water release percentage	f_p (%)	30

Airborne fraction	f_x (%)	30
Mixing rate	w_x (s ⁻¹)	0.01-1

Table 3. Core Inventory and Decay Constant parameters used for Isotopes (17).

Isotopes	Core inventory	Decay constant
Kr85M	1.19E+17	2.05E-09
Kr87	2.50E+17	1.15E-04
Kr88	3.30E+17	6.78E-05
Kr89	4.20E+17	3.64E-03
Xe131m	4.00E+16	6.74E-07
Xe133	3.61E+17	1.53E-06
Xe137	5.58E+17	3.02E-03
I131	1.40E+17	9.98E-07
I132	3.40E+17	8.37E-05
I133	6.20E+17	9.26E-06
I134	7.10E+17	2.20E-04
I135	5.81E+17	2.91E-05
Te129	7.00E+16	1.66E-04
Te131	2.60E+17	4.62E-04
Te131m	2.00E+16	6.42E-06
Te132	3.20E+17	2.46E-06
Te134	6.20E+17	1.67E-07

4.3 Spray System

The spray system plays a very important role in the removal of iodine from the containment. During severe accidents, the containment sprays system removes fission products activity within the containment two hundred times within 30 min (1). The third term of Eq. (1) is partition coefficient H and E_i is spray droplet collection efficiency. *Mehboob* (18) has suggested following the kinetic model to find out the spray droplet collection efficiency.

$$E_i = 1 - \exp \left[-6 \frac{K_g \times t_d}{d \times \left(H + \frac{K_g}{K_l} \right)} \right] \quad (6)$$

$$K_g = \frac{D_l}{d} (2.0 + 0.60 \times \text{Re}^{0.5} \times \text{Sc}^{0.33}) \quad (7)$$

$$K_l = \frac{2\pi^2 D_l}{3d} \quad (8)$$

$$D_l = \frac{(7.4 \times 10^{-8}) \times \sqrt{XM_l} \times T}{u_l \times \nu^{0.6}} \quad (9)$$

In the above expressions, t_d is a droplet exposure time, d is droplet diameter, K_g is gas-phase mass transfer coefficient, K_l is liquid phase mass transfer, Re is Reynold number, Sc is Schmidt number, D_l is iodine diffusion coefficient, M_l is molar weight, $T(K)$ is temperature, X is the degree of solvent, u_l is the viscosity of liquid water and v is molecular volume. The values of important parameters for the spray system are listed in the Table 4.

TABLE 4. Parameters for spray droplet collection efficiency (18)

Parameters	Symbols	Values
Gas-phase mass transfer coef.	K_g (cm/s)	50-0.001
Partition Coefficient	H	200 (pH=5.0)
Reynold Number	Re	1.29
Schmitt Number	Sc	1.742
Molar weights of solvent	M_l (g/mole)	18.01528
Temperature	$T(K)$	80+273.15=353.15
Molecular volume of iodine	v (cm ³ /g)	71.5
Viscosity	u_l (centipoise)	0.35
Degree of solvent	X	2.6 for H ₂ O
Exposure time	t_d (s)	10-100
Droplet size	d (micron)	100

4.4 Initial Boundary Condition

Initial boundary conditions to solve the coupled differential equations are given below

$$q_s(t) = 0, \text{ when } t=0$$

$$q_v(t) = f_f \times f_p \times f_c \times f_x \frac{A_c}{V}, \text{ when } t=0$$

5. Computation Approach

For the assessment of source term for SMR pressurized water reactor, a MATLAB program has been developed using Runge Kutta 4th order method which solved coupled differential equation. This program simulates four elements of each isotope considering the containment surface and volume. Loss of coolant accident is taken as reference. Each element has different parameters and time condition is applied which evaluate each isotope up to 1800 second in the containment air and on the containment surface. The explanation of the program is given below.

When the program start, it decides which element of an isotope is required to simulate. After making a decision, the program takes another decision that it requires data for isotope (constant parameters and values) because every element have different parameters for source term analysis. It reads the input file of data for

isotopes. After gaining data, the initial boundary condition and time steps condition are applied to the program. Then program simulates and stores the results. At this stage, the first loop is completed for one isotope. Again, the program decides for the next isotope, and the next loop starts. The program completes the result and stores it. After storing all results of isotopes. The program displays the graph. After displaying all the graphs and it stop. Fig.1 represents the block diagram of the program.

Figure 1. Block diagram of MATLAB program

6. Results and Discussions

6.1 In-Containment Activity

First, volumetric activity is evaluated in the containment air for SMR pressurized water reactor for noble gases (Xe, Kr). A spray system does not help to remove the noble gases from containment air during an accident. In this program, the core damage fraction is taken 50% and the activity which becomes available after the accident is kept at 20%. The HIPA and Charcoal filters are used, and their efficiencies are 98% and 90% respectively. In these calculations, volumetric activity is considered as the activity in the containment air. The surface activity represents the activity on the containment surface. Therefore, a comparison of these two activities is investigated for each element of all their isotopes.

Fig. 2 represents the volumetric and surface activity of xenon isotopes in the containment after an accident. Fuel release fraction and water release fraction are taken as 100% and 95% respectively for noble gases. All the simulations are performed over 30 minutes after the accident when melted core inventory comes out from all directions into the containment. Therefore, time is taken as a references x-axis. On the y-axis, volumetric and surface activity are taken reference because these two factors are related to containment. Overall activity in the containment volume increases swiftly then decreases exponentially when it reaches peak values. It is also depicted that Xe-133 as its activity becomes equal to approximately 2.75×10^{12} Bq/m³ up to 300 seconds

then decreases slowly. The activity reaches to approximately 1.75×10^{12} Bq/m³ at 1800 seconds. While this behavior is different for Xe-137 because it attains a peak value approximately equal to 2.75×10^{12} Bq/m³ at 100 seconds then decreases abruptly reaches to approximately zero level at 1800 seconds. But Xe-131m activity increases slightly becomes constant up to 1800 seconds. On the containment surface, Xe-133 activity started from zero and constantly increases concerning time up to 4.00×10^9 Bq/m² but for Xe-137 it slightly increases becomes constant at value 1.5×10^9 Bq/m².

Figure 2. In-Containment activity for Xenon isotopes

Fig. 3 depicts the volumetric and surface activity of krypton isotopes in the containment. It has been estimated that overriding activity was found for Kr-88 in the containment air. It reaches the highest value at 2.50×10^{12} Bq/m³ at 300 seconds approximately then decreases gradually throughout the given time. The least influence is found for Kr-89 in which peak activity found 2.00×10^{12} Bq/m³ at 100 seconds sharply reaches to zero level. While the behavior of these two krypton isotopes is different on the containment surface. As time increase, the activity of Kr-88 & Kr-89 also increases.

The leakage rate through the exhaust is kept at $14.15 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ while at the same time air recirculation rate through the containment is kept $4.179 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. Fuel release fraction and water release fraction are taken as 90% and 30% respectively for iodine. The deposition velocity of elemental iodine is very far greater than noble gases deposition velocity. Moreover, the spray system plays a very important role to remove the iodine from the containment. It removes almost 90% iodine. In the present case, the value of spray flow rate is made as zero because so that the true behavior of iodine isotopes could be evaluated for SMR. Fig. 4 represent that the performance of iodine isotopes activity on the surface and volume is the same, but it differs in order of magnitude. The highest activity found (i.e. among iodine isotopes) in the containment air for I-134 is 1.40×10^{12} Bq/m³ at 300 seconds but the least is found for I-131. While highest activity found on the containment surface for I-34 is 8.00×10^9 Bq/m² at 300 seconds which decreases gradually up to 1800 seconds. In sum, activity in the containment air is greater than 3 orders of magnitude as compared to containment surface.

Figure 3. In-Containment activity for Krypton isotopes

Tellurium isotopes release as fission fragments in the containment air during the severe accident. The activity of Te isotopes is shown in fig. 5. The dominant value among Te isotopes is Te-134 which has 2.25×10^{11} Bq/m³ at 300 seconds in the containment air which decrease slowly up to 1800 second. The least activity found among Te isotopes is Te-131m which increases slightly and becomes constant all over time. The same behavior is found for the same Te isotopes on the surface but as this time activity is less in order of magnitude than in the air.

Figure 4. In-Containment activity for Iodine isotopes

Figure 5. In-Containment activity for Tellurium isotopes

6.2 Effect of f_x

As described earlier, f_x is an activity which available just after the accident. In the previous case, only 20% activity is considered as available instantaneously and $(1-f_x)$ is an activity available throughout coolant after the accident in the containment. Fig. 6 represents the activity of iodine I-131 with different f_x values. I-131 is chosen as reference iodine isotope because, during a loss of coolant accident at TMI-2, the activity of I-131 was found in the containment. In the present case, 10% to 90% of f_x with different fractions is chosen on containment air and surface. In containment air, when f_x is 10% then the activity is low before 300 seconds as time increase it represents high activity according to fig. 6 (square black box is on top after 300 seconds on volumetric activity). The f_x is 90% then it is becoming less after 300 seconds (diagonal square black box is blowing after 300 seconds). This means when a higher concentration of activity is available in the core after an accident then low will be activated in the containment. Similar behavior is found for containment surface but at this time activity is less than 2 orders of magnitude than in the air.

Figure 6. The in-containment activity of I-131 with a different fraction of f_x

6.3 Effect of L_r

Fig. 7 depicts the effect of different exhaust flow rates in the containment. It is noted that when a nuclear accident occurs then containment pressure changes abruptly, due to which fission products release from the containment in the same way. The exhaust system of containment plays a very crucial role in this regard. When the exhaust flow rate is $1 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ then activity reaches to $3.00 \times 10^{11} \text{ Bq/m}^3$ at 300 seconds then decreases gradually throughout the time in containment air reaches at $2.75 \times 10^{11} \text{ Bq/m}^3$ at 1800 seconds approximately. Whereas during full operation of exhaust system (i.e. $14.15 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$), value decrease to $1.75 \times 10^{11} \text{ Bq/m}^3$ at 1800 which is half of the initiation of the exhaust system. On the containment surface, when the flow rate is $1 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ then activity reaches $1.60 \times 10^9 \text{ Bq/m}^2$ at 1800 seconds and during full operation of the exhaust system, the activity values decrease to $1.00 \times 10^9 \text{ Bq/m}^2$ at 1800 seconds. So, the level of activity in the containment air is high as 2 orders of magnitude as compared to the containment surface. The exhaust system also shows a trend toward the removal of fission products in the containment air. The exhaust system not only removes fission products at a higher flow rate, but also reduces the containment pressure as well as.

Figure 6. The in-containment activity of I-131 with a different fraction of L_r

6.4 Effect of R_{air}

Fig. 8 signify the different air recirculation flow rate in the containment. The air recirculation system of PWR has high efficient particulate air removing system or charcoal filters which tend to remove 99% particulate from the system. When any nuclear accident happens, they fully operate to hold the circumstances. Charcoal absorber has 33% to 99% efficiency to remove organic iodide. Moreover, they are also equipped with heaters and demisters to remove humidity from the containment during an accident. They are very effective during an accident, but they are not designed to hold large particulate. The high operating value of air recirculation is $4.179 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ but in the present case, the values are started from zero to large value to investigate the activity. The concentration is found in the containment $2.11 \times 10^{11} \text{ Bq/m}^3$ at 1800 seconds approximately when the air recirculation flow rate is zero. The activity level decreases up to $1.75 \times 10^{11} \text{ Bq/m}^3$ at 1800 seconds

approximately when it fully operates.

Figure 7. The in-containment activity of I-131 with a different fraction of R_{air}

6.5 Effect of w_x

Fig. 9 denote the activity of I-131 with different mixing rates in the containment. w_x is the mixing rate due to which fission products mix with coolant. The Eq. (3) is represented as negative exponential due to which activity decrease inside the containment. Due to the loss of coolant accident, melted zirconium reacts with steam to produce hydrogen gas. This reaction is the endothermic reaction in which intense heat is in the containment (16). Due to this reaction, coolant temperature increase rapidly then complex reactions occur. The mixing rate also depends upon coolant temperature, pH value, coolant pressure, the reaction rate (14). Therefore, in fig. 9 different values of mixing rates are chosen. Fig. 9 shows that a small change of mixing causes an increase in activity abruptly in the containment air or on the surface. Similarly, a mixing rate is 0.001 m/s then the peak value in the air is 2.00×10^{11} Bq/m³. Similarly, when mixing rate is 0.1 m/s then peak value reaches to 3.25×10^{11} Bq/m³ at 100 seconds then decrease gradually and reaches to 2.00×10^{11} Bq/m³ at 1800 second approximately. On the containment surface, activity at 0.001 m/s mixing rate becomes 1.00×10^9 Bq/m² and throughout time becomes constant. During 0.1 m/s mixing rate, it increases sharply at 1.8×10^9 Bq/m² at 100 seconds and decrease to 1.00×10^9 Bq/m² approximately.

Figure 8. The in-containment activity of I-131 with a different fraction of w_x

6.6 Effect of Spray Flow Rate

Fig. 10 represent the effect of spray flow rate in the containment. It is reported in NUREG-1465 that containment spray helps to remove the airborne activity in the containment equal to 2 orders of magnitude within 1800 second when both spray trains are operable (1). Therefore, spray flow is investigated in fig. 10. Initial value over the surface is zero but it has some value in the containment air according to boundary conditions. The reactor under investigation is II generation pressurized water reactor. In this type of reactor, spray system consists of two spray trains. Each train is divided 100 spray nozzles per header. They are located at 42 m height. Simulation is carried out with first zero flow rate then $1 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ with pH 5.0 keeping in view containment surface and volume. Figure 10 proves that spray system significantly reduces the airborne concentration in the containment. The collection efficiency also plays very vital role to reduce the concentration. Here droplet collection efficiency is taken as 33.4% for 100 μm droplet size. As Eq. (6) describe that droplet collection efficiency depends upon droplet size, atmospheric and droplet temperature. This formula also defines that as droplet size increase, efficiency decreases. During loss of coolant accident, when atmospheric temperature reaches to 353 K then spray system activated and starts working. When spray flow rate is 0 the activity in containment air and on surface is $1.90 \times 10^{11} \text{ Bq/m}^3$ & $1.05 \times 10^9 \text{ Bq/m}^2$ respectively at 1800 second. During spray flow rate of $1 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, then activity in the containment air and on surface is $1.88 \times 10^9 \text{ Bq/m}^3$ & $1.07 \times 10^7 \text{ Bq/m}^2$ respectively at 1800 seconds. The activity level decrease 2 orders of magnitude both containment surface and volume. Which is exact according to NUREG-1465 report.

Figure 9. Effect of spray flow rate in the containment activity

6.7 Comparison of SMR with other Reactors

In last case, a comparison of I-131 activity of SMR is made with 10 MWe Pakistan Atomic Research Reactor (PARR-1) and 1000 MWe two loop pressurized water reactor (B&W) in fig. 11. *Awan et al. (18)* was investigated typical 10 MWe material test reactor. In this type of reactor, core damage possibility is takes 80% (f_c) and airborne activity is taken as 50% (f_x). In research reactor, there is very rare possibility of loss of coolant accident. Top curve with square black box represent the 10 MWe PARR-1 which was investigate by *Awan et al. (18)*. The below curve with triangle black box depicts the activity of I-131 for 1000 MWe pressurized water reactor (B&W) studied by *Mehboob et al. (14)*. In this case, core damage is taken 50% (f_c) and airborne activity is taken as 20% (f_x). Middle curve with round black dot represent 300 MWe SMR I-131 activity. In this case, same conditions were applied as for 1000 MWe. The activity for 10 MWe increase to 5.00×10^8 Bq/m³ at 200 second approximately then decrease to 2.75×10^8 Bq/m³ at 1800 second. While the activity of SMR goes to peak 2.75×10^{11} Bq/m³ at 300 second and decreases slowly at 1.75×10^{11} Bq/m³ at 1800 seconds. The concentration level of 1000 MWe is 2.00×10^{12} Bq/m³ at 1800 second. By comparing SMR with other reactors, it is found that activity level of SMR is hundred time less 1000 MWe and three hundred times greater than research reactor. This difference is due to initial core inventory. Core inventory (A_c) depends upon reactor power level and reactor operational time. The figure describes astonishing results by comparing SMR with other reactors.

Figure 10. Comparison of SMR with 10 MWe Research Reactor and with 1000 MWe Commercial Reactor

7. Conclusion

Source term analysis has been evaluated for SMR under loss of coolant accident. A MATLAB program is developed using the Runge-Kutta 4th order method which simulates four elements of each isotope keeping in view the containment air and on the containment surface. Results show that

1. The activity of noble gases in the containment air is more as compared to on the containment surface. But on the surface, activity increase as time increases.
2. The behavior of other fission products is the same on the containment surface and volume. But its concentration in the air is greater as compared to the surface.
3. Source term also analyze by taking a different fraction of airborne activity, air recirculation rate, leakage through the exhaust, and different mixing rate. It is found from results that when the exhaust system and air recirculation system are in full operation during the loss of coolant accident then activity decreases. When the mixing rate is low, then the activity is also low. As the mixing rate becomes high then activity sharply increases in the containment then decreases gradually concerning time.
4. The spray system also helps us to remove the fission products within the containment air up to 2 orders of magnitude in 30 minutes which satisfied our results according to the NUREG-1465 report.
5. In the end, a comparison of SMR is made with research reactor and commercial 1000 MWe reactors. Results show that SMR activity level is high as compared to research reactor and low concerning commercial reactor.

This model can also be used to evaluate the containment performance and analysis of other actinides fission products for SMR.

8. References

1. USNRC. Accident Source Terms for Light-Water Nuclear Power Plants Light-Water Nuclear Power Plants. 1995.
2. IAEA. Safety Reports Series [Internet]. Vol. 53. 2008. Available from: <http://www.iaea.org/books>
3. Sehgal BR. Nuclear Safety in Light Water Reactors: Severe Accident Phenomenology. First Edi. Elsevier; 2012.
4. Beard AM, Benson C, Bowsher BR, Dickinson S, Nichols A., Beattie IR, et al. Fission Product and Aerosol Behaviour within the Containment Final Report. Luxembourg; 1990.
5. Brilliant G, Marchetto C, Plumecocq W. Annals of Nuclear Energy Fission product release from nuclear fuel I . Physical modelling in the ASTEC code. Ann Nucl Energy [Internet]. 2013;61:88–95. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2013.03.022>
6. Awan SE, Mirza NM, Mirza SM. Kinetic study of fission product activity released inside containment under loss of coolant transients in a typical MTR system. Appl Radiat Isot [Internet]. 2012;70(12):2711–9. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apradiso.2012.08.002>
7. Ullah S, Awan SE, Mirza NM, Mirza SM. Source term evaluation for the upgraded LEU Pakistan Research Reactor-1 under severe accidents. Nucl Eng Des [Internet]. 2010;240(11):3740–50. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2010.08.017>
8. Waqar S, Mirza NM, Mirza SM. Comparative study of actinide and fission product inventory of HEU and potential LEU fuels for MNSRs. Prog Nucl Energy [Internet]. 2009;51(1):129–34. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2008.02.002>
9. Mirza SM, Khan A, Mirza NM. Post-shutdown decay power and radionuclide inventories in the discharged fuels of HEU and potential LEU miniature neutron source reactors. Ann Nucl Energy [Internet]. 2010;37(5):701–6. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2010.02.001>
10. Anvari A, Safarzadeh L. Assessment of the total effective dose equivalent for accidental release from the Tehran Research Reactor. Ann Nucl Energy [Internet]. 2012;50:251–5. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2012.07.002>
11. Sadeghi N, Sadrnia M, Khakshournia S. Radiation dose calculations for an accidental release from the Tehran Research Reactor. Nucl Eng Des [Internet]. 2013;257:67–71. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2013.01.004>
12. Raza SS, Iqbal M. Atmospheric dispersion modeling for an accidental release from the Pakistan Research Reactor-1 (PARR-1). Ann Nucl Energy. 2005;32:1157–66.
13. Pappas C, Ikonopoulou A, Sfetsos A, Andronopoulos S, Varvayanni M, Catsaros N. Derivation of the source term, dose results and associated radiological consequences for the Greek Research Reactor - 1. Nucl Eng Des [Internet]. 2014;274:100–17. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2014.04.008>
14. Mehboob K, Park K, Khan R. Quantification of in-containment fission products source term for 1000 MWe PWR under loss of coolant accident. Ann Nucl Energy. 2014;
15. Lamarsh JR, Baratta AJ. Introduction to Nuclear Engineering. Third. New Jersey: Prentice Hall; 2001. 783 p.
16. Almenas K, Lee R. Nuclear Engineering. First. Berlin: Springer-Verlag; 1992.
17. Iqbal MJ, Mirza NM, Mirza SM. Kinetic simulation of fission product activity in primary coolant of typical PWRs under power perturbations. Nucl Eng Des. 2007;237(2):199–205.
18. Mehboob K, Aljohani MS. Progress in Nuclear Energy Modeling and simulation of radio-iodine released inside the containment as result of an accident. Prog Nucl Energy. 2016;88:75–87.

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.

